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A STUDY ON NOTABLE TRANSGENDER ENTREPRENEURS WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

Misconceptions are many among the ordinary populace as a part of gender dysphoria. Gender refers to the variation of characteristics, attitude and roles typically connected with biological sex – often placed on a gamut between masculine and feminine. But a mishmash of these two genders in an individual will absolutely differentiate from a common man. They are called Transgenders. They are the least group having the largest risk. The degree of risk starts from the very basis of life. To be very crystal clear, when every individual probe for the future career and prospects of life, it is at this moment that these people are in real search of their own gender identity to understand who they are. Being secluded from family, social stigma, school drop outs, illiterate, unemployed, poverty, prone to corporal abuse, homelessness, health hazards, nullified credentials, arrest on false allegations, psychological trauma, suicidal attempts, economic curb and political inability, coupled with HIV, prostitution, nabbing and trafficking (human and child). Besides all these back set the footprints of transgenders are marching ahead in the financial progression as being entrepreneurs and living a regal life. Entrepreneurial spirit is characterized by innovation and risk-taking. The present study is conducted with the aim to empower the lives of Transgender community. This article examines on the knowledge based problems faced by them.

Keywords: Transgender, Entrepreneurs, economic progression and innovation

INTRODUCTION

Profession as a viable sex worker is a trademark attached to transgender. Entrepreneurship can offer levels of accomplishment and achievement that are hard matched with employment. More recently, the term entrepreneurship has been extended to social entrepreneurship, political entrepreneurship, or knowledge entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship refers to self-employed, business owners who fit in to racial or ethnic minority faction. Entrepreneurial ventures offer an innovative product, process or service. These activities differ substantially depending on the type of organization involved. The Hijras have uprooted themselves in adopting various marketing strategies and are equally able to withstand the cut throat competition in Coimbatore. These ensure in their divine boost in social status and are naturally self- employed. This literally probe transgender to avoid anti-social and illicit elements to which they are landmarked and now they have expressed to be unique. One important success factors of transgender entrepreneurs is the ability to come up with a concept, to envision and execute it effectively. They are now growing entrepreneurs of the nation and prove their worthiness in being updated in technology, create a sense of innovation and are able to face both physical and mental hardships and track a record in the history of transgender entrepreneurial development.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To understand the concept of transgender.
2. To analyze the knowledge based difficulties faced by transgender.
3. To offer suggestions based on the findings of the study.

METHODOLOGY

Pilot Study is a preliminary study conducted on a limited scale before the original studies are carried out in order to gain some primary information and to know about the nature and different aspect of the problem. A well structured questionnaire was carefully administered followed by Interview schedule is a part of Primary data including Coimbatore Mavatta Thirunangaigal Nala Sangam is the welfare association council for Transgender. Simple Random Sampling method was undertaken in the study. Secondary Data includes books, magazines, journals, periodicals, newspapers, posters, TV channels and other related websites.

AREA COVERAGE AND SAMPLE SIZE

The major city of Tamil Nadu, The Manchester of South India “Kovai” also called as Coimbatore is the area of the study. The sample size is 110 covering 13 blocks including Municipal Corporation of Coimbatore District

Source: Primary Data

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr. Venkatrama Raju D. and Beena K. S.¹ (2015) in their article observes that in a pioneering effort to solve the problems faced by transgender people, the government of Tamil Nadu established a transgender welfare board in April 2008. Social welfare minister will serve as the president of the board. This effort is touted to be the first in India and even in the world. The government has also started issuing separate ration cards for transgender people. In additional effort to improve the education of transgender people, the Tamil Nadu government also issued an order on May 2008 to create a third gender for admissions to government colleges. The issues faced by transgenders are discrimination, lack of educational facilities, unemployment, lack of shelter, lack of medical facilities like HIV care and hygiene, depression, hormone pill abuse, tobacco and alcohol abuse, problems relating to marriage, property, electoral rights and adoption.

M.K. Ananth² (2015) reported that the members of Mavatta Thirunangaigal Nala Sangam organised a signature campaign in Gandhipuram on account of Human Rights Day. They said in many government and educational institution forms there is no appropriate column for their sex. Besides this, they want a three per cent reservation in government jobs and a national welfare board for transgenders – with a transgender as a member – to understand their problems and redress them. The association secretary S. Poonguzhali says that the attitude towards them is seeing gradual change. About the signature campaign, she said that close to 350 men and women of all age groups signed for their cause. “It will be sent to the District Legal Service Authority, who will forward it to authorities concerned,” she added. Some of the Mavatta Thirunangaigal Nala Sangam members say that they are saddened that a big chunk of society still thinks of them as beggars or people involved in illegal flesh trade. The association claims that there are more than 450 of them living in Coimbatore, Mettupalayam, Pollachi, Annur, Anamalai and Kinathukadavu.

TRANSGENDER – AN OVERVIEW

¹ Dr. Venkatrama Raju D. and Beena K. S. (2015) “A Study on Socio- Economic Issues of Third Genders in Tamilnadu”, International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR), Volume 4, Issue 7, p. 1354 – 1357, ISSN (Online) : 2319-7064,

² [M.K. Ananth](#) (2015) “Transgenders want equal opportunities”, The Hindu, Updated: December 11, 2015 09:52 IST Coimbatore.

Transgender people are called as Thirunar. Thirunangai for transfeminine people and Thirunambi for transmasculine people. They are usually called as Aravaani in Tamil and can also be called as Ali, Jagappa. Tamil Nadu has an estimated population of more than 30,000 transgender people. The highest number of transgender recorded is in Salem District and in Coimbatore alone there are 400 who have been registered and 1000 of them are yet to be registered. Most transgender of Coimbatore territory are entrepreneurs and show keen interest in cooking business. Tamil Nadu State in India was the first to introduce a Transgender Welfare Policy.

KNOWLEDGE BASED HITCHES OF TRANSGENDER

The following are the various difficulties of transgender entrepreneurs who have knowledge base issues.

1. Lack of investment patterns
2. Lack of saving habits
3. Lack of idea on government assistance
4. Lack on insurance policy
5. Lack on awareness of banking schemes
6. Lack of marketing ideas

APPLICATION OF TOOLS: GARRETT’S RANKING TECHNIQUE

To find out the most significant factor which influences the respondents, Garrett’s ranking technique is used. As per this method, respondents have been asked to assign the rank for all factors and the outcome of such ranking have been connected into the score value with the help of the following formula:

$$\text{Percentage Position} = \frac{100 (R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_j}$$

Where

R_{ij} = Rank given for the i^{th} variable by the j^{th} respondents.

N_j = Number of variables ranked = 8

With the help of Garrett Table, the percentage position estimated is connected into scores. Then for each factor the score of each individual are added and then total value of score and mean values of score is calculated. The factors having the highest mean value is considered to be the most important factor.

TABLE 1(a) : Calculation of Percentile Position

Rank	Percentile Position	Garrett’s Table Value
1	$100 (1 - 0.5) / 6 = 8.33$	77
2	$100 (2 - 0.5) / 6 = 25$	63
3	$100 (3 - 0.5) / 6 = 41.66$	54
4	$100 (4 - 0.5) / 6 = 58.33$	46
5	$100 (5 - 0.5) / 6 = 75$	37
6	$100 (6 - 0.5) / 6 = 91.66$	23

Source : Primary Data

The percentile position of ranks 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and their corresponding Garrett's table value is shown in the above table, where the calculated percentage position is 8.33 for Rank 1 and the table value is 77. Likewise for all the calculated percentage position the table values are referred from Garrett's Ranking Table.

TABLE 1 (b) : RATING EFFECTIVENESS OF FACTORS

S.No	Factors	Assigned Rank								Total Respondents	Total Score	Mean Score	Rank
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8				
1	Lack of investment	9	3	6	6	5	6	12	63	110	3802	34.56	6
2	Deficit saving habits	10	6	7	13	26	15	19	14	110	5075	46.13	5
3	No idea about govt assistance	49	18	6	14	2	12	7	2	110	7105	64.59	1
4	No knowledge on insurance policy	8	11	32	16	15	22	6	0	110	5961	54.19	4
5	Unaware of banking schemes	11	53	22	1	5	8	6	4	110	6702	60.92	3
6	Problems of marketing	13	50	22	1	9	7	6	2	110	6763	61.48	2

Source: Primary Data

FINDINGS

1. Out of 110 respondents 45 are belonging to the age group of 26-34 years.
2. On the basis of qualification 47 respondents possess primary education only.
3. 76 respondents reported to be biryani caterers, 19 respondents have preferred tailoring as their occupation.
4. 40 respondents possess the monthly income ranging Rs 5001-Rs 10,000.
5. 80 respondents have their living arrangement among TG's.
6. It is observed from the above table that transgender respondents ranked the first factor that they have no idea about the government assistance prevailing and the least preferred among the transgender is lack of savings followed by investment habits.

SUGGESTIONS

- i. It is scowl to evaluate and discriminate people who are unusual from the stereotype,
- ii. Governments should grant loans to all TG's uniformly.
- iii. Transgender entrepreneurs should have their autonomous SHGs and NGO Advisory Councils and Co-operative banks so that there is all time mobility of funds and can help in boosting more entrepreneurship among transgender.
- iv. Training and Development Programmes needs to be enhanced regularly.

- v. Financial Literacy campaign has to be organized among transgender entrepreneurs so as to promote saving and investment habits.
- vi. Banking schemes and insurance policies should be made aware and demonstration may take place for their better enhancement.
- vii. All proper credentials to avail financial and other mechanism.
- viii. Limiting the withdrawal from co-operative banks can also promote the saving habit among the transgender entrepreneurs.
- ix. Officials must concentrate more and make periodical monthly assessment report on financial learning and literacy of transgenders to identify the weaknesses and scope among them.
- x. A minimal amount is fixed as a part of savings in terms of daily or weekly basis can boost the rationality of transgender within and as a whole.

CONCLUSION

The most prevalent and discrete exploration of transgender activism is taking place in all sphere of living. A well structured Government-funded vocational rehabilitation programs must be initiated so that the transgender entrepreneurs can improve their skill set margin and this can completely eliminate them from sex drive, prostitutions, drug addictions. Live and Let Live is the phenomenon of humanity and trans community is slowly being viewed in a new light and has a vivid prosperous growth of entrepreneurship with well advancement of technology and other innovative modules which benefit the entrepreneurs, transgender community, society and the whole of the nation.

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